

PARALINGUISTIC MEANS OF EXPRESSING EMOTIONALITY AND EXPRESSIVENESS IN VERBAL COMMUNICATION

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In modern linguistics, paralinguistic means are viewed not as peripheral accompaniment to verbal communication, but as a special layer of symbolism that ensures the precise interpretation of meaning during communication. The relevance of paralinguistics stems from the fact that emotionality and expressiveness, traditionally associated with vocabulary and style, are often encoded in real communication primarily through voice, pauses, tempo, facial expressions, and gestures. These parameters form the "expression plan" of the speaker's attitude toward the message, the addressee, and the situation, and also serve as a mechanism for managing the interlocutor's attention and expectations. It should be noted that emotionality as a psycholinguistic and pragmatic category does not completely coincide with expressiveness. Emotionality is associated with the expression of the speaker's experiences and evaluative attitudes, while expressiveness aims to enhance the impact and expressiveness of the utterance. However, in real speech, these phenomena often interact and overlap, forming a unified communicative effect. The theoretical basis of the study is based on the concept of a multi-level organization of communication, in which verbal and nonverbal components interact according to the principle of complementarity and partial interchangeability. In paralinguistics, it is customary to distinguish between vocal (prosodic and timbral) and kinesic means, as well as proxemic and taketic components. However, for the analysis of emotionality and expressiveness, prosody and kinesics are the most significant, as they directly participate in marking the evaluation, intensity of experience, and communicative attitudes of the speaker. The pragmlinguistic approach allows us to consider paralinguistic markers as part of the speech act. They not only complement the meaning of the utterance, but also predetermine the way in which it will be interpreted by the addressee. In this context, intonation, pause, and speech tempo play a crucial role, shaping the structure of speech intent and determining the nature of the utterance's perception [2]. Methodologically, the study draws on a discursive understanding of emotions and expression. These manifest not only as a person's internal states but also as socially recognized patterns of behavior, enshrined in the communicative norms of a particular community. For the Uzbek speech space, where norms of politeness and respectful distance play an important role, paralinguistic devices are particularly significant. The intonational and rhythmic organization of speech often serves to soften directives, express modesty, or, conversely, demonstrate the speaker's confidence [1].

Prosodic means form the most flexible mechanism for expressing emotions. Intonation, pitch range, intensity, timbre, and duration of sounds create an acoustic image of the utterance, from which the addressee reconstructs the speaker's attitude. Increased intensity and range often correlate with increased expressiveness, but loudness alone is not always an indicator of emotionality. The context of communication and the appropriateness of the selected parameters to the communicative situation play an important role. Speech tempo and pauses

also possess significant meaning-distinguishing potential. Acceleration of tempo can signal emotional arousal, persistence, or a desire to dominate the conversation, while slowing down and lengthened pauses often indicate doubt, the importance of information, or an attempt to control the emotional state. In phonetic studies, prosody is considered a carrier of not only grammatical but also modal-evaluative meanings [2]. Kinesic means, including facial expressions, gestures, gaze direction, and posture, form the visual level of communication. In face-to-face interactions, they often prove more persuasive to the addressee than verbal content. Gestures can serve an illustrative function, enhance the meaning of a statement, regulate the order of remarks, or serve as an indicator of the speaker's emotional state. It is important to distinguish between spontaneous and socially normed gestures. Some kinesic manifestations are an involuntary response to an emotional state, while others are used consciously as a means of rhetorical influence. Nonverbal signals are integrated into the structure of social interaction and are subject to rules of appropriateness [6]. Therefore, the same gesture or facial pattern can be interpreted differently depending on the discourse genre and the communicative situation. Of particular interest is the relationship between paralinguistics and verbal content. In most cases, their congruence is observed, with nonverbal components enhancing the meaning of words. Evaluative vocabulary, accompanied by appropriate intonation and gesture, enhances the perlocutionary force of a statement and makes it more persuasive. However, cases of incongruence are also possible, when paralinguistic cues conflict with the verbal level. In such situations, the phenomenon of hidden expression arises: neutral words, pronounced with a certain timbre or accompanied by micro-facial expressions, can express irony, doubt, or hidden disagreement. Such communicative strategies allow the speaker to convey an assessment indirectly, avoiding direct confrontation [5].

Such mechanisms are particularly characteristic of Uzbek communicative culture. Expressiveness is often transferred to the paralinguistic sphere, while the verbal level remains formally neutral and correct. This helps maintain social balance and uphold norms of respectful communication. The scientific novelty of this approach lies in its consideration of emotionality and expressiveness as the result of the interaction of verbal and paralinguistic communication channels. In each specific speech act, one of these channels can play a dominant role. For example, in public speech, prosody becomes the leading factor, while in dialogic communication, visual cues acquire great significance.

To describe this interaction, it is appropriate to use the concept of a paralinguistic profile of an utterance—a set of prosodic and kinesic characteristics that regularly correlate with certain types of speech intentions. From a functional perspective, such profiles can vary depending on the discourse genre. Academic speech is characterized by reduced expressiveness and greater intonational restraint, whereas everyday dialogue allows for a wide range of emotional variations.

An important aspect is the issue of norms and deviations in the use of paralinguistic devices. Expressiveness is often interpreted as a deviation from a neutral speech pattern, but neutrality itself is culturally and historically conditioned. The same gestures or intonational strategies can be interpreted differently in different communicative cultures.

In the Uzbek-Russian bilingual space, this problem is particularly pronounced. The transfer of familiar paralinguistic patterns from one language to another can lead to pragmatic

misunderstandings. Therefore, the study of paralinguistic devices is important not only for theoretical linguistics but also for intercultural communication and the development of verbal competence. In conclusion, it should be emphasized that paralinguistic devices form an independent, yet closely related to the verbal level, mechanism for expressing emotionality and expressiveness. Their primary function is to modify the illocutionary force of an utterance, convey implicit evaluations, and regulate interpersonal distance. Thus, emotionality and expressiveness in speech should be viewed not only as a reflection of the speaker's internal state but also as an important tool of social interaction that can be systematically described within the framework of modern communication linguistics.

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